

Gaze behaviour reveals how cross-linguistic differences in case alignment shape the dynamics of sentence planning

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Abstract

In recent years, evidence has accumulated that the particular grammatical properties of a language can exert a strong influence on sentence production processes. We extend this work to investigate how differences in case marking alignment affect the time course of sentence planning. So-called nominative-accusative languages use the same case (the nominative) to mark the agents of transitive and intransitive verbs, while ergative languages use a dedicated case (the ergative) to exclusively mark the agents of transitive verbs. Previous research suggests that ergative case alignment induces earlier relational encoding at the outset of formulation, because speakers must determine the “who-does-what-to-whom” structure of the event early on to select the appropriate case marker on the initial argument. In previously studied languages, however, ergative case marking is conditioned by various language-specific grammatical factors beyond transitivity, leaving it unresolved whether it is ergativity itself which drives earlier relational encoding or some other co-dependent grammatical property of the languages tested. To address this question, we conducted a picture description task with speakers of Yéli Dnye, a language isolate of Papua New Guinea with Agent-Patient-Verb (APV) word order and strictly ergative case marking, and Japanese, an APV language with nominative-accusative case marking. Speakers of the two languages described scenes depicting transitive (two-participant) events while their eye movements were recorded. Results showed that in the earliest time window, associated primarily with conceptual encoding, Yéli Dnye speakers prioritised relational encoding to a greater degree, as evidenced by more distributed fixations to the agent and patient in the pictured events, while Japanese speakers prioritised the encoding of the sentence-initial agent argument. This pattern of results suggests that case alignment differences on their own can induce differences in the earliest stages of sentence formulation.

Keywords: sentence production, ergativity, eye tracking, cross-linguistic comparison, case marking typology, Papuan languages

1 Introduction

When we speak, we transform what we want to communicate into a sequence of words (Bock & Ferreira, 2014; Konopka & Brown-Schmidt, 2014; Levelt, 1989). In principle, speakers could proceed with this transformation in a linear fashion, where they plan one increment (e.g., a word or a phrase) at a time and build the utterance's grammatical structure as they proceed, or in a hierarchical fashion, where they first construct a relational plan that reflects the 'who-did-what-to-whom' content of the message and which is subsequently enriched with lexical material (linear vs. hierarchical incrementality; Bock & Ferreira, 2014; Norcliffe & Konopka, 2015). There is evidence that speakers, in fact, rely on both strategies for planning sentences, depending on a variety of factors, such as the ease of encoding and expressing (the preverbal) message (e.g., Esaulova, Penke, & Dolscheid, 2019; Konopka & Meyer, 2014; Konopka, Meyer, & Forest, 2018; van de Velde, Meyer, & Konopka, 2014) or individual cognitive differences (e.g., Swets, Fuchs, Krivokapić, & Petrone, 2021; Swets, Jacovina, & Gerrig, 2014).

In recent years, work extending language processing research to more diverse and understudied languages has highlighted the crucial role that grammar plays in sentence planning (Jaeger & Norcliffe, 2009; Norcliffe, Harris, & Jaeger, 2015). For example, in the verb-initial languages Tzeltal (Mayan, Mexico) and Tagalog (Austronesian, Philippines), the order in which information about event characters is encoded in transitive sentences is shaped by word order and by the (non-adjacent) dependencies that are marked in the morphological form of the verb from the earliest stages of formulation. In Tzeltal, relational information about the action denoted by the verb is encoded earlier when speakers plan a verb-initial compared to an agent-initial sentence (Norcliffe, Konopka, Brown, & Levinson, 2015). In Tagalog, the verb signals the role of the (usually) sentence-final argument, leading the specific relation between the verb and its argument to be encoded early (in addition to the early relational encoding induced by verb-initial word order; Sauppe, Norcliffe, Konopka, Van Valin, & Levinson, 2013). In addition, when planning similar utterances in the Australian language Murrinhpatha, in which all possible orders of verbs and arguments are permitted, speakers show a strong preference for encoding relational information at the outset of sentence planning

instead of prioritising the encoding of a single referent. The authors suggest that, compared to strict word order languages, “the option to freely order constituents places additional pressure on Murrinhpatha speakers to develop a conceptual representation of the event relatively early in sentence planning” (Nordlinger, Garrido Rodriguez, & Kidd, 2022, p. 213). 35

Here, we turn our attention to how cross-linguistic differences in one specific grammatical feature, case marking alignment, influence the time course of sentence planning. Languages differ in whether and how they express grammatical dependencies between verbs and their arguments. Some languages use case marking to signal the grammatical relationship that a dependent noun bears to its verbal head. Case-marking systems themselves show great variability across languages (cf., Bickel & Nichols, 2009, for a typological overview). In nominative-accusative languages, the agent argument of transitive verbs and the sole argument of intransitive verbs are marked with the same case, the nominative, while the patient of transitive verbs are marked distinctly, with accusative case (as in English pronouns, which distinguish nominative and accusative forms, e.g., *He_{S.NOM}} sleeps* vs. *He_{A.NOM}} sees *him_{P.ACC}}*). Thus, sole arguments of intransitive verbs and agent arguments of transitive verbs are aligned in their case marking in these languages. In ergative languages, by contrast, the sole argument of intransitive verbs and the patient of transitive verbs are aligned, i.e., marked in the same way, whereas agents of transitive verbs are singled out with a special case marker, the ergative (for overviews, see Bickel, 2010; Bickel & Nichols, 2009; Dixon, 1979; see example 1 below). In the study reported here, the linguistic contrast of interest concerns the distinct way that agent and patient arguments are marked in transitive (two-participant) sentences in a language with a nominative-accusative case alignment system compared to a language with an ergative case alignment system. 40 45 50 55*

Recently, evidence has accrued that ergative case marking can induce a more relational (hierarchical) mode of planning at the outset of sentence formulation, compared to nominative-accusative marked structures. For example, Hindi (Indo-European, India) is a language that has ergative case marking, but crucially, its presence is conditioned by the aspect of the verb. In the perfective aspect (describing events as completed), agent arguments of transitive verbs are marked 60 65

with the ergative case, while the sole arguments of intransitive verbs carry the unmarked nominative case. In the imperfective aspect (describing events as ongoing), both agents and sole arguments carry the unmarked nominative case. Sauppe et al. (2021) took advantage of this within-language contrast to examine the effect of different case marking patterns on planning processes. In an eye-tracked picture description task, they found that when preparing to describe transitive scenes with perfective sentences with sentence-initial, ergative-marked agents, Hindi speakers engaged in more extensive relational encoding early in the planning process (between 200 and 800 ms after picture onset). The prioritisation of early relational encoding was evidenced by more distributed fixations to agents and patients (i.e., a lower likelihood of speakers fixating the first-mentioned agent character preferentially, cf. Konopka, 2019; Konopka & Meyer, 2014), compared to unmarked nominative sentences in the imperfective.

These planning differences are plausibly induced by the particular affordances of different case marking alignments. When preparing to produce a sentence in the perfective aspect, Hindi speakers need to make an early decision about the case associated with the initial noun phrase. This choice depends on the verb's transitivity: In the perfective aspect, an ergative-marked noun phrase only allows a transitive sentence structure. Accordingly, Hindi speakers need to make a structural commitment early in the planning process in such contexts, which requires engaging in more extensive relational encoding at the outset of formulation. By contrast, in the imperfective aspect, where both transitive sentences' agents and intransitives' sole arguments are unmarked, speakers can defer such a structural commitment. This deferral is possible because an initial unmarked noun phrase leaves the possibility for a variety of different continuations (based, for example, on accessibility, cf. Ferreira, 1996; Tanaka, Branigan, McLean, & Pickering, 2011).

Another type of ergativity is found in Basque, where all semantic agents are marked with the ergative (Laka, 2006), including not only agents of transitive verbs (e.g., *hit*), but also semantic agents of intransitive verbs (e.g., *jump*), in contrast to the sole participants of non-controlled events (such as *fall*), which are marked by absolutive (nominative) case. Ergative case marking is independent of the verb's syntactic transitivity—a so-called “active” or split-intransitive case

marking alignment (Bickel & Nichols, 2009). Egurtzegi et al. (2022) found that the requirement to select the appropriate case marking on the initial noun phrase led Basque speakers to also make an early structural commitment, compared to German (where the initial noun phrases are usually unmarked). Similar to Hindi speakers, Basque speakers distributed their visual attention during picture description more between agents and patients when planning sentences with ergatives, indicating early relational encoding.

In sum, the presence of ergative case marking in a language appears to induce more extensive early relational planning because speakers need to encode multiple types of relational and linguistic information early on in order to decide on the morphological form of the first argument (i.e., whether to mark it with ergative or with nominative case). The relationship between a sentence's verb and its arguments underlies this early emphasis on relational encoding. Such planning requirements would, by hypothesis, prevent speakers from using radically linearly incremental planning strategies (i.e., planning word by word; Bock & Ferreira, 2014; Gleitman, January, Nappa, & Trueswell, 2007) for these kinds of sentence structures.

However, in the languages studied so far, ergative case marking is conditioned by multiple factors that go beyond the basic relational information of "who-did-what-to-whom". In Basque, the event semantics and lexically specified argument structure of the verb determine case marking (Laka, 2006). In Hindi, case marking depends on grammatical aspect in conjunction with transitivity (Mohan, 1994). It is thus conceivable that the extensive relational encoding observed for ergative-marked sentences in these languages stems (at least partially) from those language-specific grammatical factors. In Hindi, when preparing to describe a transitive event, speakers need to encode aspectual information to determine case assignment to the agent, for which affectedness of the patient may be an important cue, potentially driving increased attention to the patient in the early stages of sentence formulation. In Basque, it may be necessary to retrieve the verb lemma and its argument structure in an early time window, because ergative case assignment is conditioned by verbal argument structure (Egurtzegi et al., 2022; Santesteban, Pickering, Laka, & Branigan, 2015).

This raises the question of whether the encoding of relational information is always prioritised when preparing sentences with ergative case marking, compared to unmarked sentences in nominative languages (like German or English), or whether it would not be observed in languages with consistently ergative grammars. In such “strictly” ergative languages, the use of ergative case is determined solely by the syntactic transitivity of the clause, such that all and only agent arguments of two-participant verbs are marked with the ergative. On the one hand, it is possible that only shallow encoding of relational information is necessary if speakers simply need to decide on the transitivity of the clause. In this scenario, no extensive encoding would be required, as basic relational information can be extracted from images rapidly (in less than 100 ms; Dobel, Gumnior, Bölte, & Zwitserlood, 2007; Hafri, Trueswell, & Strickland, 2018; Isasi-Isasmendi et al., 2023; Sauppe & Flecken, 2021). On the other hand, the need to determine the number of event participants and the transitivity of the upcoming verb could induce more extensive relational planning by comparison with languages where all initial agent arguments, regardless of the transitivity of the verb, are marked the same way. This would be because there is no consistent one-to-one mapping between the number of event participants, which can be rapidly encoded, and the number of arguments suitable verbs may take (Levin, 1999).

To answer this question, we compare the time course of sentence formulation in Yélí Dnye and Japanese, two languages that provide a grammatical contrast allowing a direct test of these hypotheses, in an eye-tracked picture description experiment (cf. Norcliffe & Konopka, 2015). Yélí Dnye, a language isolate of Rossel Island (Papua New Guinea), is an ergative language that does not exhibit splits in case marking and that is consistently ergative throughout its grammar. In Japanese, by contrast, agent arguments of both transitive and intransitive verbs are marked with the nominative case. Critically, the linear structure of simple declarative transitive sentences is identical in both languages: Morphological case markers are attached to the right edge of the noun phrase and the basic word order is agent-patient-verb (APV, also called SOV, for subject-object-verb; cf. Dryer, 2013). These shared features allow for a comparison between two “strict” case-marking languages while keeping other relevant grammatical factors constant. Additionally, because the basic word order is the same in both languages, we

sidestep the need to use a sentence-completion task to elicit the same order in both languages (as in Egurtzegi et al., 2022), therefore allowing for more spontaneous and naturalistic picture descriptions. 165

1.1 Case marking alignment in Yélf Dnye and Japanese

Yélf Dnye (sometimes abbreviated to Yélf)¹ is spoken by approximately 4000–5000 people on Rossel Island, Papua New Guinea (see Fig. 1). The grammar has been described by Henderson (1995) and more recently by Levinson (2022). 170

Figure 1: Location of the Yélf Dnye speaker community on Rossel Island in the Louisiade Archipelago of Papua New Guinea.

Yélf Dnye uses predominantly an agent-patient-verb word order, though other word orders are possible and noun phrases are frequently dropped when their reference is clear from the context. Tense, aspect, mood, and person/number of agent and patient arguments are indexed on the verb by means of clitics.

While many Papuan languages have optional or flexible ergative case marking (Foley, 2018), in Yélf Dnye all overtly realised agent arguments of transitive verbs strictly carry ergative case. The ergative is marked at the right edge of the noun phrase with the enclitics (=ngê for singular and =y:oo for dual/plural). 175

¹The language's glottocode is yele1255, <https://glottolog.org/resource/language/id/yele1255>.

Sole arguments of intransitive verbs and patient arguments of transitive verbs are
180 unmarked (see example 1).

- (1) a. kî pi lèpî
this person go
“The man is going.”
b. kî pi-ni=ngê kma y:enê
this person-DEF=ERG frog caught
“The/this man caught a frog.”²

185 Japanese also has a basic agent-patient-verb word order, but shows
nominative-accusative case marking alignment: Agent arguments of (active)
transitive verbs and the sole argument of intransitive verbs are marked with a post-
nominal nominative case particle.³ Thus, every sentence in the basic word order
(i.e., non-scrambled word order; cf. Yamashita, 2002) begins with a nominative-
190 marked noun phrase. The patient argument of transitive verbs is marked by an
accusative case particle (see example 2).

- (2) a. otokonohito ga aruku
man NOM walk.PRS
“A man walks.”
b. otokonohito ga kaeru o tsukamaeta
man NOM frog ACC catch.PST
195 “A man caught a frog.”⁴

In the experiment reported in the following, we tested whether the case-
marking differences between Yéî Dnye and Japanese induce differences in the
allocation of visual attention to agent and patient characters during sentence
planning. Specifically, we assess whether the production of ergative case-
200 marked agent-patient-verb sentences in Yéî Dnye is associated with more

²Abbreviations: DEF = definite, ERG = ergative case.

³If the subject is also the discourse topic, it is marked with the particle *wa*. In our experimental task, described below, which involved the description of a series of unconnected pictures that were not embedded in any larger discourse context (such that each picture consistently presented an “all-new” context), speakers did not produce *wa*-marked arguments.

⁴Abbreviations: NOM = nominative case, ACC = accusative case, PRS = present tense, PST = past tense.

extensive relational planning at the outset of sentence formulation compared to the production of nominative case-marked agent-patient-verb sentences in Japanese. We assess this by recording fixations to characters in pictures of two-participant events while speakers of the two languages viewed and described these pictures. Based on the hypothesized earlier commitment to a transitive sentence structure when preparing sentences with ergative-marked agent arguments, we predicted that Yéllí Dnye speakers would be more likely to prioritise encoding of the relational who-did-what-to-whom structure of a depicted event, so that they distribute their attention between agents and patients at the outset of planning (i.e., showing a smaller preference for the sentence-initial agent) than speakers of Japanese.

We specified two analysis time windows to cover two broad phases of the planning process. The first time window, from 200 to 800 ms after picture presentation, spanned the conceptual encoding phase, following previous cross-linguistic studies on sentence planning (Egurtzegi et al., 2022; Sauppe et al., 2021). Under a hierarchically incremental view of sentence planning, speakers are expected to identify who does what to whom in the depicted event during this phase (i.e., at the outset of planning) and thus begin to encode the relationship between the agent and the patient, as the basis for their utterance plan. Previous cross-linguistic sentence production studies showed that visual attention and eye movement patterns in this phase are already influenced by grammatical structure (Egurtzegi et al., 2022; Norcliffe, Konopka, et al., 2015; Nordlinger et al., 2022; Sauppe et al., 2021, 2013). Before 200 ms, few language-related eye movements are expected because it takes approximately this long to program and execute the first saccade into the to-be-described stimulus picture as soon as it appears (Pierce, Clementz, & McDowell, 2019; Rayner, 1998; Richardson & Spivey, 2008).

The second time window extended from 800 to 2300 ms (i.e., approximately until the grand mean speech onset at 2328 ms) and broadly covers the linguistic encoding phase. In this phase, speakers are expected to prepare and retrieve the word forms of the first referent in their utterance and to arguably begin retrieval of the word forms of the second referent (cf. Bock & Ferreira, 2014; Griffin & Bock, 2000; Norcliffe & Konopka, 2015).

Figure 2: Example stimulus picture to elicit agent-patient-verb sentences equivalent to, e.g., “A boy/man catches a frog”.

2 Method

2.1 Participants

235 Forty-five native speakers of Yéî Dnye (from Rossel Island) and 56 native
speakers of Japanese (undergraduate students at the University of Tokyo)
participated for payment.⁵ Ethical approval was obtained from the ethics
committee for behavioural and social sciences of Radboud University Nijmegen
(approval number ECG0601011).

2.2 Materials and procedure

The target stimuli were coloured line drawings of 52 transitive (two-participant)
events (see Figure 2 for an example). Eighty-five drawings of intransitive (one-
participant) events were used as fillers. The task for the participants was to
describe each pictured event when it was presented with one sentence as quickly
245 and accurately as possible, mentioning all characters and the verb expressing the
action that the character(s) were engaged in.

⁵Birth years are only sporadically recorded for speakers of Yéî Dnye, so that participants could not give their exact age. However, participants’ age range was approximately 18–45 years. Due to a technical error, participants’ ages were not recorded for Japanese participants, all of who were, however, undergraduate students.

Experimental lists were created by arranging the target stimuli in a pseudo-random order among the filler pictures. At least one intransitive picture intervened between any two transitive pictures. The orientation of the target events (with the agent positioned on the left or right side) was counterbalanced across two experimental lists by vertically mirroring the original pictures. Each participant was assigned to one list. Each list was divided into four blocks of 30–37 trials and pauses were offered after completion of each block. 250

Each trial began with the presentation of a black dot in one of five randomly assigned positions at the top of the screen. Participants were instructed to fixate this dot to ensure that their gaze did not fall on one of the event characters when the picture appeared, since this could have increased the visual salience of the characters and subsequently biased sentence planning processes by specifically facilitating the encoding of first-fixated characters in a bottom-up fashion (Dolscheid & Penke, 2023; Gerwien, Schlenter, Penke, & Konopka, 2011). In a gaze-contingent manner, the presentation of the trial’s stimulus picture was triggered once the fixation dot was looked at consecutively for 700 ms. The experiment started with a block of nine training trials for which participants heard pre-recorded example descriptions. These were followed by four additional training pictures that the participants described themselves while receiving feedback from the experimenter if necessary. 255 260 265

2.3 Data recording and analyses

Eye movements were recorded with an SMI REDm mobile eye tracker (SensoMotoric Instruments, Teltow) at a sampling rate of 60 Hz. The stimuli were presented on a laptop placed approximately 60 cm away from the participants, using the Experiment Center software of the eye tracker manufacturer. Participants’ picture descriptions were recorded with a microphone and later transcribed and annotated. The onset of the first word of the response (speech onset latency) was manually annotated in Praat (Boersma, 2001). 270 275

For the analysis of eye movements during sentence planning, areas of interest for agents and patients in the target pictures were manually defined with the

BeGaze software of the eye tracker manufacturer, which also grouped the recorded samples into fixation events. All remaining pre-processing was performed in R (R Core Team, 2025). For each trial, consecutive fixations within areas of interest were subsumed into gazes (Griffin & Davison, 2011) and then aggregated into time bins to reduce temporal autocorrelation (Barr, 2008; Cho, Brown-Schmidt, & Lee, 2018). For the 200–800 ms analysis time window, 100 ms bins were used, whereas we used 200 ms bins for the longer 800–2300 ms time window to reduce computational complexity.

Trials were excluded from analysis if participants did not produce a syntactically transitive (active) sentence with both the agent and the patient expressed overtly in agent-patient-verb word order. We further excluded sentences with patient arguments that were abstract or not depicted in the stimulus pictures, as well as responses that resulted in unfinished or ungrammatical descriptions and in which participants corrected themselves or started over. We also excluded responses with multiple clauses or verbs (such as compound verb constructions in Japanese). Responses with speech errors, deviating from the targeted case marking (Yélfí Dnye: Agent-Ergative, Patient-Absolutive; Japanese: Agent-Nominative, Patient-Accusative) were also excluded. We further excluded trials in which participants' gaze fell on the agent or patient character as the stimulus appeared (i.e., not on the fixation dot) or in which the first fixation on the agent or the patient occurred later than 400 ms after stimulus onset, as well as trials with track loss (operationalised as a gap of more than 600 ms between fixations), and trials with speech onsets longer than 3 SD than the by-participant mean speech onset. Trials were also excluded if no fixations were registered or if audio recordings were missing (due to experimenter error). If a participant was left with less than five trials after application of these criteria, we excluded them from the analyses. In addition, data were excluded from three Yélfí Dnye participants because they were accidentally presented with stimulus blocks from both lists, one Yélfí Dnye participant for whom no eye-tracking data was saved, and one Japanese participant for whom no audio recordings were saved. In total, 1444 trials were included in the analyses (Yélfí Dnye: 694 trials, Japanese: 750 trials; see Table A1).

The time course of overt visual attention during sentence planning was analysed by separately modelling fixations to the agent and the patient characters.

We fitted binomial Bayesian hierarchical regressions on the single-trial level using the `brms` (version 2.21.0) interface to Stan (Bürkner, 2017, 2018a; Carpenter et al., 2017) in R. Posterior distributions of estimates were summarised and visualised with `bayestestR` (Makowski, Ben-Shachar, & Lüdecke, 2019) and `ggplot2` (Wickham, 2016). Binomial regression is well suited for the analysis of eye movements in visual world paradigms because it takes into account the categorical nature of the data (Cho et al., 2018; Donnelly & Verkuilen, 2017; Sauppe, 2017). 315

Non-linear changes in agent and patient attention over time were modelled using linear, quadratic, and cubic orthogonalized polynomial time terms (growth curve analysis; Mirman, 2014; Mirman, Dixon, & Magnuson, 2008). These polynomials reflect the overall slope of the fixation curves (linear time), the shape of the primary inflection points (quadratic time, describing the curves as flat or “peaky”), and shifts in peak latencies (cubic time). 320

As population-level control variables, we included each trial’s speech onset latency and its interactions with the time terms, to model how faster or slower preparation of an utterance affects the distribution of visual attention over time, as well as the size of the area of interest (agent or patient) because larger characters could generally be more likely to be gazed at. Temporal autocorrelation in eye movement time courses was modelled using an AR(1) term (Brown-Schmidt, Naveiras, De Boeck, & Cho, 2020). 325 330

Continuous predictors were z -transformed (Schielzeth, 2010), except for the orthogonalised time terms, and categorical predictors were sum-coded (-1, 1). The population-level predictors (“fixed effects”) had *Student’s t* priors ($\mu = 0$, $\sigma = 2$, $df = 5$); the standard deviations of the group-level predictors (“random effects”) had exponential priors (scaling factor = 1). The maximal structures for group-level predictors as justified by design were included (as proposed for frequentist regression, Barr, 2013; Barr, Levy, Scheepers, & Tily, 2013). The models were fitted in four chains of 4000 iterations each (including 2000 warm-up iterations). 335

The influence of the language difference and its interaction with the time terms was assessed using two model-based measures. We considered an effect noteworthy if a predictor had a posterior probability mass of at least 80% above or below 0 (probability of direction, Makowski, Ben-Shachar, Chen, & Lüdecke, 2019) or if a predictor had an evidence ratio to be different from 0 (equivalent to a 340

one-sided Bayes Factor, Bürkner, 2018b) of greater than 3 (Dienes & Mclatschie, 2018). These measures are not significance thresholds in the frequentist sense, but rather indicate how probable an effect is given the data and the priors.

3 Results

Overall, Japanese speakers started speaking earlier than Yéí Dnye speakers (Japanese: grand mean speech onset = 2202 ms, SD = 525 ms; Yéí Dnye: grand mean speech onset = 2528 ms, SD = 609 ms).

Figure 3A shows the time course of agent and patient fixations during sentence planning in both languages. Speakers preferentially gazed at the agent characters shortly after picture onset and continued to do so until approximately 700 ms after stimulus picture onset. Around 700–800 ms, patient fixations approached agent fixations (even being on par in Yéí Dnye). After 800 ms, speakers of both languages continued to primarily look at the agent before turning their attention to the patient character at approximately 800–1000 ms before speech onset.

In the first 200–800 ms, speakers of Yéí Dnye distributed their visual attention more between the depicted characters than Japanese speakers, leading to fewer and later-peaking agent fixations (Agent *Language*: mean $\hat{\beta} = -0.64$, $P(\hat{\beta} < 0) = 0.83$, Evidence Ratio = 4.78; Agent *Time*³ × *Language*: mean $\hat{\beta} = 0.90$, $P(\hat{\beta} > 0) = 0.96$, Evidence Ratio = 25.14; see Figure 3B and Table A2). In turn, patient fixations of Yéí Dnye speakers also peaked earlier than those of Japanese speakers. This is indicated by patient fixations peaking and then beginning to decrease around 700 ms in Yéí Dnye, but not in Japanese (Patient *Time*³ × *Language*: mean $\hat{\beta} = -0.77$, $P(\hat{\beta} < 0) = 0.91$, Evidence Ratio = 10.02; see Figure 3B and Table A3).⁶

⁶An analysis of agent and patient fixations between 200 and 600 ms after stimulus picture onset (as used in, e.g., Norcliffe, Konopka, et al., 2015; Nordlinger et al., 2022) leads to a qualitatively similar pattern of results. In this time window, Yéí Dnye speakers fixated on agents less and with a more “peaky”, i.e., more steeply declining, likelihood than Japanese speakers (Agent *Language*: mean $\hat{\beta} = -0.72$, $P(\hat{\beta} < 0) = 0.85$, Evidence Ratio = 5.68; Agent *Time*² × *Language*: mean $\hat{\beta} = -0.80$, $P(\hat{\beta} > 0) = 0.95$, Evidence Ratio = 19.1; see Table A4). Yéí Dnye speakers’ likelihood of attending to the patient also showed a more “peaky”, i.e., more steeply increasing, trajectory than in Japanese speakers (Patient *Time*² × *Language*: mean $\hat{\beta} = 0.73$, $P(\hat{\beta} < 0) = 0.91$, Evidence Ratio = 10.01; see Table A5). That the differences in fixation behaviour between Yéí Dnye speakers

Between 800 and 2300 ms, there was also a difference in the distribution of gazes for sentences planned by Yélf Dnye and Japanese speakers. Yélf Dnye speakers, who were more likely to look away from the agent in the first analysis time window, showed an increase in agent fixations during this second time window. Specifically, Yélf Dnye speakers' fixations to agents exhibited a higher and earlier peak, before more steeply declining than Japanese speakers' agent fixations (Agent $Time^1 \times Language$: mean $\hat{\beta} = -2.00$, $P(\hat{\beta} > 0) = 0.97$, Evidence Ratio = 30.87; Agent $Time^2 \times Language$: mean $\hat{\beta} = -1.98$, $P(\hat{\beta} > 0) = 0.98$, Evidence Ratio = 44.98; Agent $Time^3 \times Language$: mean $\hat{\beta} = 0.46$, $P(\hat{\beta} > 0) = 0.77$, Evidence Ratio = 3.40; cf. Figure 3C and Table A6). In turn, Yélf Dnye speakers' fixations to patients increased more steeply and with a flatter and later inflection point than Japanese speakers' patient fixations (Patient $Time^1 \times Language$: mean $\hat{\beta} = 2.38$, $P(\hat{\beta} > 0) = 0.98$, Evidence Ratio = 52.33; Patient $Time^2 \times Language$: mean $\hat{\beta} = 2.00$, $P(\hat{\beta} > 0) = 0.98$, Evidence Ratio = 51.29; Patient $Time^3 \times Language$: mean $\hat{\beta} = -0.78$, $P(\hat{\beta} > 0) = 0.89$, Evidence Ratio = 8.43; cf. Figure 3C and Table A7).

and Japanese speakers are captured by different interactions between the language contrast and the polynomial time terms here follows from the fact that choosing a different time window means that different portions of the overall fixation curves (with a different mean shape) are to be modelled (Mirman, 2014; Mirman et al., 2008). However, this does not affect the conclusion that the results in the 200–600 ms and 200–800 ms analysis time windows are qualitatively similar.

Figure 3: Time course of agent and patient fixations during sentence planning in Yélf Dnye and Japanese. **A**: Grand mean proportions of fixations (based on by-participant means and smoothed by a simple moving average over four periods). Ribbons indicate one standard error of the mean. The dotted vertical lines indicate the analysis time windows (200–800 and 800–2300 ms after stimulus onset); the solid lines show the grand mean speech onsets for each language. **B–C**: Posterior probabilities of language-related model parameters for the 200-800 ms time window (**B**) and the 800-2300 ms time window (**C**); point ranges indicate the respective 50%, 80%, and 90% highest density intervals around the mean parameter estimates.

4 Discussion and conclusions

As the scope of cross-linguistic research on sentence production has widened, 385
evidence has accumulated demonstrating that the prioritisation of encoding
operations during sentence formulation may depend on the grammatical properties
of the language spoken (Brown-Schmidt & Konopka, 2008; Egurtzegi et al., 2022;
Momma, Slevc, & Phillips, 2016; Norcliffe, Konopka, et al., 2015; Nordlinger
et al., 2022; Sarvasy, Morgan, Yu, Ferreira, & Momma, 2023; Sauppe et al., 390
2021, 2013, i.a.). In the present paper, we contribute to this work by examining
whether and how differences in case marking alignment across languages can
influence planning processes during sentence production. In a picture description
task, native speakers of Yélí Dnye (a language from Papua New Guinea with
ergative case-marked agents) and Japanese (a language with nominative case- 395
marked agents) described pictures of simple transitive events while their eyes were
tracked. Crucially, both languages share the same agent-patient-verb word order
and mark case in the same position (at the end of the agent noun phrase). This
allowed a cross-language comparison of the influence of ergative vs. nominative
case alignment on the time course of sentence formulation, specifically on the 400
degree of early relational encoding.

We found that Yélí Dnye speakers' and Japanese speakers' gaze patterns when
planning to describe pictures of two-participant, transitive events were overall
similar, with visual attention first directed primarily to the agent and then to
the patient character. These similarities suggest that when speakers of different 405
languages produce utterances with the same agent-patient-verb order, they aim to
encode information in a comparable manner. Against this backdrop, there were
clear relative differences between the two languages: When preparing to utter a
transitive sentence, Yélí Dnye speakers showed a smaller early preference for the
agent (i.e., they were more likely to fixate both the agent and patient characters 410
in the target pictures), compared to Japanese speakers, in a planning time window
associated primarily with the encoding of event-relational information (the first
200–800 ms after a to-be-described stimulus picture was presented). In line with
previous work (Egurtzegi et al., 2022; Norcliffe, Konopka, et al., 2015; Nordlinger
et al., 2022; Sauppe et al., 2021), this gaze behaviour suggests that Yélí Dnye 415

speakers prioritised relational encoding in the early stages of sentence planning, as relational information is presumably distributed between characters in a depicted event (cf. Griffin & Bock, 2000; Konopka, 2019; Norcliffe & Konopka, 2015). Japanese speakers, by contrast, prioritised the encoding of the sentence-initial agent argument to a higher degree during this same time window.

This difference in encoding strategies is plausibly driven by differences in case marking alignment: In a strictly ergative language like Yéí Dnye, the first element of the sentence is marked with the ergative case if the verb is transitive but is left unmarked if the verb is intransitive, thereby requiring speakers to make a commitment to produce a transitive or an intransitive sentence early in the planning process (at least before preparing the phonological form of the sentence-initial noun phrase). We assume that this grammatically-driven requirement leads speakers to prioritise the encoding of event-structural information at the outset of sentence planning.

In Japanese, where almost all sentences (without dropped arguments) start with a nominative noun phrase,⁷ the encoding of the agent character can be initially prioritised over relational information, because the nominative does not commit the speaker to a particular event-structural frame (e.g., a transitive event). Rather, starting a sentence with a nominative-marked noun phrase provides speakers with the flexibility to continue with many different structures (e.g., an intransitive or a transitive sentence, a passive, etc.), so that grammatical commitments can be deferred in Japanese. This finding parallels the prioritisation of the encoding of information about the initial noun phrase in German where agents of transitive and intransitive verbs are also not differentiated by case (Egurtzegi et al., 2022). Making decisions on which grammatical structure to produce at a later time point can either mean that Japanese speakers prepare multiple possible sentence plans in parallel to some degree (cf. Brehm, Cho, Smolensky, & Goldrick, 2022; Myachykov, Scheepers, Garrod, Thompson, & Fedorova, 2013) or that Japanese speakers could afford to prepare generally smaller message increments before

⁷Sentences with scrambled word order in Japanese may place the patient first and thus begin with an accusative-marked noun phrase (“OSV” word order). However, these are quite infrequent and only used in specific contexts (Yamashita, 2002; Yano, Niikuni, Shimura, Funasaki, & Koizumi, 2025).

starting to speak (Brown-Schmidt & Konopka, 2008; Konopka & Brown-Schmidt, 445
2014).

In the later window (between 800 ms and grand mean speech onset at 2300 ms, associated with the encoding of linguistic form), Yélf Dnye speakers gazed more at the agent and less at the patient, compared to Japanese speakers. This suggests that during this time window, Yélf Dnye speakers devoted more resources to 450
the lexical encoding of the sentence-initial agent noun phrase. It is possible that the attenuation of looks to the agent during this same window in Japanese occurred because Japanese speakers had already engaged in extensive encoding of this character before 800 ms, allowing them to begin shifting their attention 455
to the patient (i.e., the second referent to be mentioned in their utterance) earlier than Yélf Dnye speakers could. It is a consistent finding in eye-tracked picture description studies that the lexical encoding of noun phrases proceeds sequentially (cf., e.g., Griffin & Bock, 2000; Hwang & Kaiser, 2014; Konopka, 2019; Norcliffe, Konopka, et al., 2015; Nordlinger et al., 2022; Sauppe, 2017; van de Velde et al., 2014). In turn, earlier planning and lexical encoding of the agent in Japanese 460
may also be one reason why Japanese speakers were, on average, ready to begin articulation earlier than Yélf Dnye speakers.

The apparent case-driven differences in the earliest stages of sentence formulation are in line with previous eye tracking studies that have found an influence of ergative case marking alignment on sentence planning. For Hindi, 465
Sauppe et al. (2021) report that preparing sentences starting with ergative-marked agents induced more relational encoding during the earliest stage of formulation; Egurtzegi et al. (2022) found that relational information also received priority in the planning of sentences with ergative-marked agents in Basque (compared to German sentences with nominative-marked agents). This cross- 470
linguistic parallelism speaks against an alternative interpretation of the current results—namely that the observed differences in gaze behaviour are due to non-linguistic factors driven by differences in the populations under study (e.g., lack of experience with computers or with participating in experiments in the case of the Yélf Dnye participants; cf. the discussions of methodological aspects of cross- 475
linguistic, “field-based” experiments in Næss & Sauppe, 2025; Polinsky, 2023;

Sauppe, Andrews, & Norcliffe, 2023; Speed, Wnuk, & Majid, 2017; Wagers & Chung, 2023).

480 Previous studies investigating the role of ergativity on the time course of sentence formulation have focused on languages with different kinds of ergative case marking systems. For these languages, the possibility has remained open that the early relational encoding observed in the planning of ergative-marked sentences could be (partially) due to other factors (e.g., in Hindi, the need to encode aspectual information). Yélfí Dnye, by contrast, exhibits “strict” morphosyntactic
485 ergativity, where agents of transitive verbs (and only those) are marked with the ergative case, without exception. The difference in eye gaze patterns between Yélfí Dnye and Japanese speakers thus suggests that case alignment differences on their own can induce different planning routines in the earliest stages of sentence formulation.

490 The fact that these case-induced planning differences are found within the first 800 ms of sentence formulation, a time window primarily associated with conceptual processing, is noteworthy. According to top-down models of sentence production, conceptual-level encoding unfolds without access to information encapsulated at linguistic levels of formulation (Bock & Levelt, 1994; Garrett,
495 1988; Levelt, 1989). Instead, the tight relation observed between fixation patterns and case marking suggest that conceptual-level processes and those related to linguistic formulation may not be strictly separated. Previous production studies involving within- and cross-language comparisons support this conclusion (e.g., Brown-Schmidt & Konopka, 2008; Norcliffe, Konopka, et al., 2015), implying
500 that grammar can guide the time course of sentence planning from early message preparation onward.⁸

An important remaining question concerns how far “down” in the production system ergative case exerts an influence on formulation, for instance, whether it also influences lexical retrieval. Based on the distributed fixation pattern within
505 the first 800 ms in the current study, we infer that Yélfí Dnye speakers engage in more extensive early relational encoding compared to Japanese speakers, despite

⁸Kurumada and Jaeger (2015) argue that in Japanese even the potential ambiguity of a sentence and the goal to be understood are weighted off already during early encoding of grammatical structures.

the fact that the verb itself occurs last in the language. Do Yéí Dnye speakers also routinely select and retrieve a verb lemma at an early stage of planning (despite its sentence-final position), or is (rudimentary) relational encoding sufficient for deciding on the case of the initial noun phrase?

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For nominative-accusative languages, there is some evidence suggesting that verbs are not necessarily planned in lexical detail early in verb-final sentences. Picture-word interference studies have not found delays in speech onset latencies in the production of verb-final word orders when verb distractors are presented (Hwang & Kaiser, 2014, for Korean, and Schriefers, Teruel, & Meinshausen, 1998, for German). Momma et al. (2016) find that in Japanese, verbs are planned before the articulation of patient arguments, but not before the articulation of agent arguments, by comparing interference effects in patient-verb sentences (i.e., with an unrealised, dropped agent) to interference in intransitive sentences. While these findings leave open the timing of verb planning in the current kind of naturalistic picture description using sentences without dropped arguments, they suggest that in Japanese verb-final structures, verbs are not necessarily retrieved before their agent argument.⁹

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For ergative languages, fewer studies have addressed the question. For Basque, Egurtzegi et al. (2022) argue that because the verb specifies which argument is treated as an agent (following the analysis in Laka, 2006), speakers need to encode some information about the verb early in the planning process in order to decide whether to prepare an ergative-marked or unmarked sentence-initial noun phrase. Basque speakers must therefore retrieve information about the verb's argument structure before planning the initial argument and its case marking, as indicated by increased neural synchronisation in the EEG theta frequency band, which suggests early access to verb information in the lexicon, presumably to encode the argument structure. In addition, based on structural priming evidence, Santesteban et al.

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⁹Furthermore, the picture-word interference paradigm always aims to distract or interfere with the planning of specific verbs, and in this way are informative about the timing of lexical encoding and lemma retrieval. This experimental method therefore cannot directly address the question of whether decisions about general semantic or syntactic properties of suitable verbs (e.g., the decision to use an intransitive vs. a transitive verb, or which broad semantic class of verbs to consider) are made early. Unfortunately, the current eye-tracking findings from Yéí Dnye and Japanese and from previous studies on the planning of ergative case marking (Egurtzegi et al., 2022; Sauppe et al., 2021) are also not sufficient to resolve this question, and so it must await further study.

(2015) propose that selection of the verb precedes constituent structure building
535 in Basque. Thus, further cross-linguistic research is required to establish to what
extent and how differences in case marking alignment influence the timing of verb
planning.

The results accrued so far, on diverse languages such as Yélf Dnye, Hindi, and
Basque, show that the pattern of planning of sentences beginning with ergative-
540 marked agents goes in hand with signs of extensive early relational encoding in eye
gaze behaviour, suggesting that in this domain there is a cross-linguistically stable
link between eye gaze and linguistic information processing. In this regard, there is
an interesting contrast with what has been observed for language comprehension,
where predictive processes, as indexed by eye-gaze behaviour, have been observed
545 to be influenced by literacy (cf., e.g., Huettig & Pickering, 2019; Huettig, Singh, &
Mishra, 2011; Mishra, Singh, Pandey, & Huettig, 2012). Given that literacy is not
widespread in Yélf Dnye (Levinson, 2022), the current body of production results
suggests that the link between the uptake of visual information and grammatical
structure during spoken sentence production may not be affected by literacy in the
550 same way.

To conclude, the current study contributes to extending the empirical base of
research on language processing, which is still very much focused on a small set of
well-studied languages (Jaeger & Norcliffe, 2009; cf. also Kidd & Garcia, 2022).
That such an extension is essential for a comprehensive understanding of human
555 language and how it is processed and represented becomes clear when looking at
the diversity of the languages of the world, on every level of linguistic structure
(Blasi, Henrich, Adamou, Kemmerer, & Majid, 2022; Evans & Levinson, 2009;
Levinson, 2012; Levinson & Evans, 2010; Majid & Levinson, 2010; Norcliffe,
Harris, & Jaeger, 2015; Sinnemäki, 2014, i.a.). Here, we have focused on Yélf
560 Dnye's ergativity, in comparison to Japanese's nominative-accusative system, as
a test of the influence of case alignment on sentence planning. This, of course,
barely scrapes the surface of what Papuan languages might offer psycholinguistic
theory building. Papua and the New Guinea area have the greatest density of
languages in the world and exhibit a tremendous degree of linguistic diversity, both
565 in terms of the number of languages spoken in the area (almost 20% of the world's
languages) and in the number of independent language families (Foley, 2000;

Palmer, 2018). However, only recently have psycholinguists begun to conduct controlled studies of real-time language processing in Papuan languages (see Mulak, Sarvasy, Tuninetti, & Escudero, 2021; Sarvasy et al., 2023, for Nungon). Our understanding of language processing (and the interaction of grammar and cognition in general) will undoubtedly benefit from a more concerted study of the languages of the New Guinea area. 570

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the European Research Council Advanced Grant No. 269484 and the Max Planck Society for the Advancement of Science (S.C.L.),
575 Swiss National Science Foundation grant No. PZ00P1_208915 (S.S.), and the European Commission's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 836921 (E.N.). The authors thank Tayo Neumann and Atsuko Takashima for assistance with Japanese data collection and annotation, Gabriela Garrido Rodríguez for help with data preprocessing, and
580 Antje S. Meyer for institutional support. The map in Figure 1 was made with data from Natural Earth ([naturalearthdata.com](https://www.naturalearthdata.com)).

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

585 Data availability

Analysis scripts and models are available at https://osf.io/vzc4g/?view_only=7dc74a8497324006acf5e0fe331839a5.

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595 Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Appendix

A.1 Overview of trial exclusions

Reason for trial exclusion	Yéfi Dnye	Japanese
No fixations registered	22	48
Response deviating from target structure (e.g., word order was not agent-patient-verb, dropped argument, compound verb construction, case marking error, abstract or non-depicted patient)	853	1548
Already fixated at agent/patient character position at stimulus onset	126	153
First agent/patient fixation >400 ms	549	326
Track-loss	415	609
Speech onset outlier	30	45
Participant left with less than 5 trials	9	10
No audio recording (due to experimenter error)	451	303
Total number of usable trials excluded	1421 (67.2%)	1938 (72.1%)

Table A1: Overview of trial exclusion criteria and absolute numbers of trials they apply to. Application of criteria was unordered and individual trials could fulfil multiple exclusion criteria. Usable trials were those trials potentially available for analysis, after exclusion of whole participants and after removing trials for which no audio recordings or eye tracking data were available.

A.2 Regression model summaries

Table A2: Posterior parameter estimates from Bayesian binomial growth curve regression predicting the likelihood of agent fixations over time for the planning of sentences in Yélfí Dnye and Japanese in a time window of 200–800 ms after stimulus picture onset. We report $P(\hat{\beta} > 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} > 0$ and $P(\hat{\beta} < 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} < 0$.

Predictor	Mean $\hat{\beta}$	SE	Credible Interval		$P(\hat{\beta})$	Evidence Ratio
			10%	90%		
Intercept	0.77	0.90	-0.71	2.24		
Time ¹	0.25	1.37	-1.96	2.53		
Time ²	-2.31	0.83	-3.67	-0.95		
Time ³	3.00	0.40	2.34	3.66		
Language (= Yélfí Dnye)	-0.64	0.68	-1.76	0.48	$P(< 0) = 0.83$	4.78
Language \times Time ¹	0.50	1.10	-1.29	2.32	$P(> 0) = 0.67$	2.05
Language \times Time ²	-0.19	0.82	-1.56	1.17	$P(< 0) = 0.59$	1.46
Language \times Time ³	0.90	0.51	0.06	1.74	$P(> 0) = 0.96$	25.14
Speech onset (standardized)	-0.41	0.58	-1.36	0.55		
Speech onset \times Time ¹	-0.90	0.80	-2.21	0.42		
Speech onset \times Time ²	-1.06	0.62	-2.08	-0.05		
Speech onset \times Time ³	-0.23	0.48	-1.04	0.57		
Agent AOI area (standardized)	1.01	0.61	0.01	2.02		
AR(1)	0.82	0.01	0.80	0.83		

Table A3: Posterior parameter estimates from Bayesian binomial growth curve regression predicting the likelihood of patient fixations over time for the planning of sentences in Yéli Dnye and Japanese in a time window of 200–800 ms after stimulus picture onset. We report $P(\hat{\beta} > 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} > 0$ and $P(\hat{\beta} < 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} < 0$.

Predictor	Mean $\hat{\beta}$	SE	Credible Interval		$P(\hat{\beta})$	Evidence Ratio
			10%	90%		
Intercept	-7.20	1.21	-9.16	-5.16		
Time ¹	7.54	2.49	3.37	11.57		
Time ²	-5.77	0.84	-7.15	-4.41		
Time ³	1.34	0.47	0.57	2.14		
Language (= Yéli Dnye)	0.33	0.75	-0.93	1.56	$P(> 0) = 0.67$	2.05
Language \times Time ¹	0.01	1.19	-1.96	2.00	$P(> 0) = 0.50$	1.00
Language \times Time ²	-0.12	0.77	-1.38	1.17	$P(< 0) = 0.56$	1.30
Language \times Time ³	-0.77	0.58	-1.71	0.19	$P(< 0) = 0.91$	10.02
Speech onset (standardized)	-0.32	0.68	-1.44	0.78		
Speech onset \times Time ¹	0.59	0.92	-0.90	2.13		
Speech onset \times Time ²	1.13	0.67	0.02	2.22		
Speech onset \times Time ³	0.58	0.57	-0.35	1.52		
Patient AOI area (standardized)	2.69	0.85	1.29	4.09		
AR(1)	0.85	0.01	0.83	0.86		

Table A4: Posterior parameter estimates from Bayesian binomial growth curve regression predicting the likelihood of agent fixations over time for the planning of sentences in Yéli Dnye and Japanese in a time window of 200–600 ms after stimulus picture onset. We report $P(\hat{\beta} > 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} > 0$ and $P(\hat{\beta} < 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} < 0$.

Predictor	Mean $\hat{\beta}$	SE	Credible Interval		$P(\hat{\beta})$	Evidence Ratio
			10%	90%		
Intercept	1.01	1.02	-0.67	2.69		
Time ¹	1.00	1.04	-0.70	2.73		
Time ²	-3.32	0.41	-3.98	-2.65		
Time ³	0.99	0.26	0.56	1.42		
Language (= Yéli Dnye)	-0.72	0.68	-1.85	0.41	$P(< 0) = 0.85$	5.68
Language \times Time ¹	0.45	0.82	-0.88	1.81	$P(> 0) = 0.71$	2.44
Language \times Time ²	-0.80	0.49	-1.61	< 0	$P(< 0) = 0.95$	19.1
Language \times Time ³	-0.02	0.40	-0.67	0.65	$P(< 0) = 0.52$	1.09
Speech onset (standardized)	-0.08	0.58	-1.01	0.89		
Speech onset \times Time ¹	0.14	0.63	-0.89	1.17		
Speech onset \times Time ²	-0.10	0.44	-0.83	0.62		
Speech onset \times Time ³	0.09	0.39	-0.54	0.72		
Agent AOI area (standardized)	1.30	0.66	0.22	2.38		
AR(1)	0.81	0.01	0.79	0.83		

Table A5: Posterior parameter estimates from Bayesian binomial growth curve regression predicting the likelihood of patient fixations over time for the planning of sentences in Yéli Dnye and Japanese in a time window of 200–600 ms after stimulus picture onset. We report $P(\hat{\beta} > 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} > 0$ and $P(\hat{\beta} < 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} < 0$.

Predictor	Mean $\hat{\beta}$	SE	Credible Interval		$P(\hat{\beta})$	Evidence Ratio
			10%	90%		
Intercept	-8.50	1.40	-10.76	-6.15		
Time ¹	8.63	1.50	6.16	11.10		
Time ²	-2.49	0.45	-3.21	-1.75		
Time ³	0.23	0.29	-0.24	0.70		
Language (= Yéli Dnye)	0.37	0.78	-0.89	1.67	$P(> 0) = 0.68$	2.12
Language \times Time ¹	0.29	0.79	-0.99	1.58	$P(> 0) = 0.64$	1.78
Language \times Time ²	0.73	0.55	-0.17	1.63	$P(> 0) = 0.91$	10.01
Language \times Time ³	-0.02	0.44	-0.75	0.70	$P(< 0) = 0.51$	1.05
Speech onset (standardized)	-0.41	0.69	-1.56	0.73		
Speech onset \times Time ¹	-1.04	0.68	-2.17	0.07		
Speech onset \times Time ²	-0.30	0.50	-1.12	0.50		
Speech onset \times Time ³	0.38	0.42	-0.30	1.05		
Patient AOI area (standardized)	3.89	1.05	2.20	5.63		
AR(1)	0.87	0.01	0.85	0.89		

Table A6: Posterior parameter estimates from Bayesian binomial growth curve regression predicting the likelihood of agent fixations over time for the planning of sentences in Yélí Dnye and Japanese in a time window of 800–2300 ms after stimulus picture onset. We report $P(\hat{\beta} > 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} > 0$ and $P(\hat{\beta} < 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} < 0$.

Predictor	Mean $\hat{\beta}$	SE	Credible Interval		$P(\hat{\beta})$	Evidence Ratio
			10%	90%		
Intercept	-0.35	0.61	-1.36	0.67		
Time ¹	-4.00	1.20	-6.00	-2.02		
Time ²	-1.91	0.87	-3.36	-0.49		
Time ³	1.14	0.45	0.38	1.87		
Language (= Yélí Dnye)	0.07	0.59	-0.89	1.01	$P(> 0) = 0.55$	1.20
Language \times Time ¹	-2.05	1.13	-3.95	-0.23	$P(< 0) = 0.97$	30.87
Language \times Time ²	-1.98	0.98	-3.59	-0.34	$P(< 0) = 0.98$	44.98
Language \times Time ³	0.46	0.60	-0.54	1.45	$P(> 0) = 0.77$	3.40
Speech onset (standardized)	0.75	0.55	-0.16	1.66		
Speech onset \times Time ¹	4.38	1.02	2.72	6.09		
Speech onset \times Time ²	1.12	0.75	-0.11	2.34		
Speech onset \times Time ³	-0.03	0.57	-0.98	0.90		
Agent AOI area (standardized)	0.44	0.46	-0.33	1.20		
AR(1)	0.74	0.01	0.72	0.75		

Table A7: Posterior parameter estimates from Bayesian binomial growth curve regression predicting the likelihood of patient fixations over time for the planning of sentences in Yélf Dnye and Japanese in a time window of 800–2300 ms after stimulus picture onset. We report $P(\hat{\beta} > 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} > 0$ and $P(\hat{\beta} < 0)$ when the mean $\hat{\beta} < 0$.

Predictor	Mean $\hat{\beta}$	SE	Credible Interval		$P(\hat{\beta})$	Evidence Ratio
			10%	90%		
Intercept	-2.34	0.60	-3.33	-1.35		
Time ¹	4.19	1.17	2.31	6.17		
Time ²	1.27	0.86	-0.12	2.71		
Time ³	-1.03	0.42	-1.71	-0.32		
Language (= Yélf Dnye)	0.07	0.59	-0.90	1.03	$P(> 0) = 0.55$	1.22
Language \times Time ¹	2.38	1.18	0.49	4.34	$P(> 0) = 0.98$	52.33
Language \times Time ²	2.00	0.96	0.45	3.59	$P(> 0) = 0.98$	51.29
Language \times Time ³	-0.78	0.62	-1.80	0.24	$P(< 0) = 0.89$	8.43
Speech onset (standardized)	-1.84	0.56	-2.76	-0.91		
Speech onset \times Time ¹	-4.77	1.04	-6.50	-3.09		
Speech onset \times Time ²	-1.21	0.76	-2.47	0.04		
Speech onset \times Time ³	0.71	0.60	-0.27	1.69		
Patient AOI area (standardized)	-0.14	0.48	-0.94	0.63		
AR(1)	0.73	0.01	0.72	0.75		